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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Glossary

CA	Consortium Agreement
CU	Comenius University Bratislava
DI/AI	Digital Innovation/Artificial Intelligence
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
ENLIGHT Alliance	ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE
ENLIGHT E+	The ENLIGHT European university alliance's project funded by the European Union's EPLUS2020 Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency programme under Grant Agreement N°101004027
ENLIGHT RISE	The ENLIGHT European university alliance's project funded by the European Union H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n°101035819
EU	European Union
FSIGN	H2020 Financial signatory at each partner institution
GA	Grant Agreement
MGA	Model Grant Agreement
NUI Galway	National University of Ireland Galway
OS	Open Science
Q&A	Quality & Assurance
REA	European Research Executive Agency
R&I	Research and Innovation
R&I SG	Research and Innovation Support Group
RUG	University of Groningen
UBx	University of Bordeaux
UGent	Ghent University
UGOE	University of Göttingen

UPV/EHU	University of the Basque Country
UT	University of Tartu
UU	Uppsala University
WP	Work package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ENLIGHT RISE management Handbook is intended to give guidelines on project management procedures for the whole ENLIGHT RISE Community to guarantee an efficient and smooth implementation of the project in order to fulfil our obligations to the European Commission.

It refers to governance and management bodies, decision-making process, internal project activity monitoring and communication, quality processes.

1. Introduction

The ENLIGHT RISE project management Handbook aims at supporting the ENLIGHT RISE community in the efficient and effective management of the project in order to guide them to ensure its good implementation.

The handbook focuses on the structure, organization, internal communication and internal procedures for the smooth implementation of the ENLIGHT RISE project. It presents how the project will be implemented, monitored.

Links with other ENLIGHT RISE/ENLIGHT E+ deliverables

This deliverable focuses on internal communication (communication between consortium members). It does not deal with communication towards external stakeholders. Such aspects are dealt with in deliverable “D9.4 - RISE Project Communication Plan”.

This deliverable recalls the communication management strategy defined for the ENLIGHT E+ project as same rules apply to ENLIGHT RISE. It recalls the ENLIGHT E+ deliverable D1.2 “Communication management Strategy”.

2. Decision making process and governance

2.1. General structure

The ENLIGHT RISE management structure is designed for the sole management and implementation of the present project. It will rely on the ENLIGHT alliance governance bodies as ultimate management structure.

The ENLIGHT RISE management structure is conceived as a monitoring system, which will “plug in” to the governance bodies of the ENLIGHT alliance, reporting to the ENLIGHT Governing Board, the ultimate decision-making body of the ENLIGHT network.

In terms of governance, we discern 3 dimensions, each with specific structures:

- the governance of the ENLIGHT alliance
- the ENLIGHT RISE project management
- the internal governance within each university.

For clarity, the full ENLIGHT alliance governance is presented, including the governance bodies specific to ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE.

2.1.1. Governance structure of the ENLIGHT alliance

2.1.1.1 Coordination of the ENLIGHT Alliance

The ENLIGHT Alliance is co-coordinated by UGent and UBx with the appointment of a full time Executive Secretary.

For overall coordination of the alliance and to secure the alignment between both the ENLIGHT E+ as the ENLIGHT RISE projects, the co-coordinating partners (UGent and UBx) and the Executive Secretary meet once a week to discuss all major alliance, ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE issues, and prioritize topics for the Directors' meeting. The Chair and Vice Chair of the Directors' meeting (DM) also take part in this weekly ENLIGHT Alliance coordination meeting (the Chair of the DM is the Directors' meeting representative of the partner institution chairing the Governing board, which is rotating every 6 months), as well as the project coordinators and project managers for both ENLIGHT programmes of both the coordinating and co-coordinating partner universities.

2.1.1.2 ENLIGHT Governing board

The ENLIGHT Governing Board is the highest decision-making body with regards to the strategy of the ENLIGHT alliance.

It consists of:

- nine (9) Rectors/Presidents;
- three (3) Student representatives (President, Vice-President and Secretary of the Student Board);
- the Executive Secretary (as observer and rapporteur);

- the Chair of the Directors' meeting (as observer and linking pin between the different structures).

All decisions made by the ENLIGHT Governing Board will be taken by consensus.

2.1.1.3 ENLIGHT Directors' Meeting

The ENLIGHT Directors' meeting is a monthly meeting gathering of one Vice-Rector/Vice-President/Director of each ENLIGHT partner university (in most instances Vice-Rectors/Vice-Presidents/Directors for Internationalization) as well as the ENLIGHT RISE coordinator and the ENLIGHT Executive Secretary.

This gathering ensures smooth communication between the ENLIGHT Governing Board and the ENLIGHT E+/ENLIGHT RISE Executive Committees and Project Boards (see below).

2.1.1.4 ENLIGHT Student Board

The ENLIGHT Student Board monitors that the proposed actions benefit all students as the main beneficiaries and co-creators of ENLIGHT. It consists of three (3) student representatives (President, Vice-President and Secretary) chosen from the Student Network.

2.1.1.5 ENLIGHT External Advisory Board

The ENLIGHT External Advisory Board reflects on the challenges Europe and the world are facing, what this means for European education and research-innovation. It advises the Governing Board on how to transform to respond to the needs of a rapid changing world and how to increase the quality and competitiveness of European higher education and research-innovation. It will be composed of six high-level societal representatives with a broad view on global developments influencing universities.

2.1.2. Governance structure of the ENLIGHT RISE project

2.1.2.1 ENLIGHT RISE Coordination Team

While for ENLIGHT E+ project UGent is the official coordinator for the European Commission with UBx as its co-lead, for the ENLIGHT RISE project, UBx is the official coordinator for the European Commission (Research Executive Agency) with UGent being the co-leader.

Henceforward, UBx shall be the intermediary between the partners and the funding authority for ENLIGHT RISE. To facilitate the overall project coordination, UBx relies on a project coordinator assisted by a project manager (*see 2.1.2.1.1-2*).

The ENLIGHT RISE Coordination Team (i.e. UBx + UGent) stays in close contact through e-mail. Alongside they hold a fixed weekly status meeting (*see 2.1.1.1*) for overall more strategic issues on an alliance level, and a monthly operational ENLIGHT RISE meeting

between the coordinating and co-coordinating academic coordinators and project managers, and ad hoc additional meetings (live or electronically) when a specific phase in the ENLIGHT RISE project or specific issues require more frequent consultations.

2.1.2.1.1 The project coordinator (UBx)

Prof. Laurent Servant (UBx) is the project coordinator of the ENLIGHT RISE project. He oversees the overall coordination and the technical development of the project. The project coordinator is the intermediary between the ENLIGHT RISE project partners and the funding authority (REA), and within the ENLIGHT alliance, she is the main spokesperson for the project, as well as the contact person vis à vis the Directors' Meeting and all other ENLIGHT alliance platforms. The project coordinator shall perform all tasks assigned to this position as described in the Grant Agreement and in the ENLIGHT RISE Consortium Agreement.

For the operational day-to-day technical coordination of the project, the project coordinator is assisted by the overall project manager (see below).

The project coordinator's counterpart at the co-coordinating university (UGent) is the UGent ENLIGHT RISE academic coordinator Dr. Dirk De Craemer (who in some fora will be relieved by the UGent ENLIGHT RISE project manager Fede Dewulf).

2.1.2.1.2 The project manager

The project manager at UBx assists the project coordinator and the ENLIGHT RISE partners on an operational level by overseeing the project lifecycle and monitoring deadlines; supporting the consortium in administrative, legal and financial issues and liaising with the REA policy officer. The project manager holds the ENLIGHT RISE Secretariat, and functions as the technical coordinator of the ENLIGHT RISE project preparing all Project Board and Executive Committee meetings (see below), and is in charge of the EU Project Portal and its correct and timely usage.

The project manager's counterpart at the co-coordinating university (UGent) is the UGent ENLIGHT RISE project manager Fede Dewulf.

2.1.2.1.3 Role of the co-coordinating partner university

The coordinating institution (UBx) is the main responsible and decision taker within the ENLIGHT RISE project, responsible for the overall operations of the project, and the ENLIGHT consortium; i.e. the day-to-day management, the external visibility, representation, contact with the funding authority and legal representation etc. The task of the co-coordinating institution (UGent) is to – upon request from UBx – advise, assist and back up as support to the coordinating institution and stands as first in line to represent the consortium upon the request of the coordinator, in particular when the latter is unavailable.

The co-ordination partners monthly (or when needed) discuss strategic matters on the state of affairs of the consortium, and/or pressing issues at hand.

2.1.2.2 ENLIGHT RISE Executive Committee

The ENLIGHT RISE Executive Committee is responsible for the overall monitoring and structural development of ENLIGHT RISE decided by the Governing Board.

It consists of:

- Vice-Rectors/Vice-Presidents/Directors for Research and/or Internationalisation and/or any other Vice-Rectors/Vice-Presidents/Directors or Head of the Grant Office relevant for the implementation of ENLIGHT RISE at each university;
- Academic and/or administrative Leaders (academic and/or administrative co-leads as deputies) of the different ENLIGHT RISE work packages;
- the ENLIGHT RISE Project Board (partly overlapping with the above) (see 2.1.2.3);
- the ENLIGHT Student Board;
- the members of the Directors' Meeting.

2.1.2.3 ENLIGHT RISE Project Board

The ENLIGHT RISE Project Board reports to the ENLIGHT RISE Executive Committee and is responsible for overall project management, reporting and financial management, quality insurance liaising with the funding authorities, developing the different work packages under coordination of the WP Executive Teams and managing communication and dissemination.

It consists of:

- the ENLIGHT RISE official Coordinator;
- the ENLIGHT Executive Secretary;
- Each partner university's main ENLIGHT RISE liaison;
- the ENLIGHT RISE operational Work Package leaders (project coordinators) and co-leads:
 - o WP1: UT (co-lead UBx and RUG)
 - o WP2: UGent (co-lead UBx and UPV/EHU)
 - o WP3: UU (co-lead UBx, UGOE and UT)
 - o WP4: CU (co-lead UGent and NUI Galway)
 - o WP5: NUI Galway (co-lead UU and CU)
 - o WP6: RUG (co-lead UPV/EHU and CU)
 - o WP7: UGOE (co-lead UT and UGent)
 - o WP8: UPV/EHU (co-lead NUI Galway)
 - o WP9: UBx (co-lead UGent and UGOE)

2.1.2.4 ENLIGHT RISE Work Package Executive Teams

The ENLIGHT RISE WP Executive Teams are responsible for monitoring and discussing the progress of the work packages and evaluating the expected deliverables.

It consists of:

- one (1) coordinating and one or more co-coordinating Work Package lead (from each of the co-leading partners for the corresponding Work Package);
- Task Experts (at least one representative from each university).

One leading partner along with one to three (generally two) co-leading partners have been nominated for each work package with a clear distribution of tasks. The leading institution has the final responsibility over the execution of the work package, sharing personnel resources for coordination and serving as liaison between the WP members. All partners actively participate in all work packages and WP tasks. They appoint key staff members to ensure the active involvement for their institution.

The list of WPs is available in the section 3 *“project workplan and implementation”*.

Roles and obligations of each partner are specified in the ENLIGHT RISE Consortium Agreement.

2.1.3. Internal Governance within each university

The ENLIGHT RISE Project Coordination Team at each partner's institution is responsible for monitoring the university-wide internal involvement across the different work packages of ENLIGHT RISE at each partner's institution.

It includes, at each partner institution:

- a dedicated person appointed by their institution (either the institutional representative in the ENLIGHT RISE Executive Committee, or one of the Academic Leaders)
- main liaison in the ENLIGHT RISE Project Board
- all key persons that represent their university in one of the ENLIGHT governing bodies.

Per work package or group of actions separated local working groups can function.

Institutional Project Coordination Teams ensure optimal communication and synergies between the ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE projects within their own institution.

2.2. Function, frequency and reporting of project management and governance bodies

ENLIGHT Governing Board	
Meeting frequency	2x per year (physical on occasion of ENLIGHT General Meeting and ENLIGHT mid-year meeting)
Composition	Rectors/Presidents Student board ENLIGHT Executive-Secretary (as observer and rapporteur) Chair of the Directors' meeting (as observer and linking pin between the different structures)
Reports to	N/A
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deciding on the ENLIGHT alliance strategy and long-term objectives ○ Deciding on governance and legal status of the ENLIGHT alliance ○ Giving direction to the overall development of the ENLIGHT alliance ○ Reflecting on points raised by the student board ○ Reflecting on advice provided by the EAB
ENLIGHT Directors' meeting	
Meeting frequency	Monthly, each second Thursday of the month
Composition	Vice-Rectors/Vice-Presidents/Directors for Internationalisation (one per institution) ENLIGHT Executive Secretary (as observer and rapporteur)
Reports to	Governing Board
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Preparing strategic issues for decision by the Governing Board ○ Deciding about budgetary shifts with impact on the overall budget division ○ Discussing problems and possible remediation signalled by project Board ○ Discussing overall development of ENLIGHT alliance ○ Identifying linkages between ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE initiatives ○ Identifying links and interdependencies across WP/Tasks and specific deliverables, and facilitating cooperation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Validating achievement of milestones ○ Validating Project Deliverables to be uploaded in the EC portal ○ Validating interim and final report ○ Deciding on adaptations of the Consortium Agreement of separate projects within the alliances ○ Deciding on (the request of project amendments; e.g. with respect to deliverables)
ENLIGHT External Advisory Board	
Meeting frequency	At least 1x per year (physical, on occasion of ENLIGHT General Meeting), but invited to each Governing board
Composition	Societal representatives; chair of the board of directors
Reports to	Governing Board
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reflecting on the global challenges, and what this means for higher education and research-innovation; ○ Advising the ENLIGHT alliance on how to transform in order to better educate future agents-of-change and serve the needs of a rapid changing world; ○ Advising the ENLIGHT alliance how to increase the quality and competitiveness of European Higher Education and Research-Innovation; ○ Advising the ENLIGHT alliance on strategies to ensure sustainability of the alliance
ENLIGHT Student Board	
Meeting frequency	2x per year (physical on occasion of ENLIGHT General Meeting and ENLIGHT mid-year meeting)
Composition	President, Vice-President and Secretary appointed by the Student Network
Reports to	Directors' meeting; Governing Board
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Representing the Student Network in the semi-annual Governing Board and Directors meeting ○ Reflecting on the interests and ambitions of students in the ENLIGHT alliance ○ Formulating the student recommendations on an annual basis ○ Initiating meetings and activities of the Student Network
ENLIGHT RISE EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE	

Meeting frequency	2x per year (physical on occasion of ENLIGHT general Meeting and ENLIGHT mid-year meeting)
Composition	Vice-Rectors/Vice-Presidents/Directors for Research and/or Internationalisation and/or any other Vice-Rectors/Vice-Presidents/Directors or Head of the Grant Office relevant for the implementation of ENLIGHT RISE project at each university; ENLIGHT Executive Secretary; Academic and/or administrative Leaders (academic and/or administrative co-leads as deputies) of the different ENLIGHT RISE work packages; ENLIGHT RISE Project Board; ENLIGHT Student Board
Reports to	Governing Board
Function	Overall monitoring and structural development of the progress made in the ENLIGHT RISE project
ENLIGHT RISE Project Board	
Meeting frequency	Monthly
Composition	ENLIGHT RISE Project coordinator ENLIGHT Executive secretary Main project liaisons ENLIGHT RISE WP leads and co-leads for each institution
Reports to	Directors' meeting
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Monitoring the progress of tasks, deliverables, budget, indicators for all WP (based on up-to-date content in the dedicated project management tools) ○ Signalling delay regarding project tasks and deliverables and discussing possible mitigations ○ Identifying issues causing delay and/or hampering the implementation of a task and/or deliverable ○ Preparing progress and/or cost-efficiency issues for decision by the Directors' Meeting ○ Preparing budgetary issues for decision by the Directors' Meeting ○ Preparing proposals for remedial action and for decision by the Directors meeting ○ Preparing periodic reports
ENLIGHT RISE CO-COORDINATION MEETINGS	

Meeting frequency	Weekly, each Monday
Composition	Chair and Vice Chair of the Directors' meeting Vice-Rectors/Vice-Presidents/Directors for Research and/or Internationalisation of the co-coordinating institutions ENLIGHT Executive secretary Academic Project coordinators of ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE projects Project managers of the coordinators and co-coordinators of the ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE projects
Reports to	Directors' meeting
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Discussing all issues related to the overall coordination of the alliance ○ Prioritizing topics for the directors' meeting.
ENLIGHT RISE WP EXECUTIVE TEAMS	
Meeting frequency	Depending on WP and Tasks implementation, defined by WP lead
Composition	WP Leader and co-leads WP task members/experts from each partner university
Reports to	Project Board Meeting; ENLIGHT RISE Project Coordination
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Defining the overall planning for the implementation of the WP ○ Coordinating the implementation of the project tasks ○ Monitoring progress of the project tasks and timely implementation ○ Monitoring the composition and matching of profiles of the task teams across the ENLIGHT RISE partner institutions ○ Alert the Project Board Meeting in case of deliverable/budget deviation
ENLIGHT RISE INSTITUTIONAL PROJECT COORDINATION TEAM	
Meeting frequency	Defined by each institution
Composition	Chaired by a dedicated person appointed by their institution Main liaison in the Project Board All key persons that represent their university in one of the ENLIGHT RISE governing bodies

	Per work package or group of actions separated local working groups can function
Reports to	Directors' meeting, Executive committee, WP Executive Teams, Project Board, ENLIGHT RISE Coordination
Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Assigning the right people profiles to specific roles (WP Leader, WP Contact, WP Coordinator, Task Leader, Task Contact) ○ Appointing and ensuring internal single point of contact/communication that ensures the communication between ENLIGHT alliance and the institution ○ Ensuring the adequate internal follow-up of the ENLIGHT RISE project content ○ Alerting the ENLIGHT RISE representatives in the Boards on possible points of attention from the own institution ○ Preparing institutional input required for the WP/Tasks ○ Monitoring the expenses of the own institutions in the framework of the ENLIGHT RISE project ○ Translating the decisions of the ENLIGHT RISE Boards to the own institution

The persons listed for the ENLIGHT RISE project in the different governance bodies can be found in the ENLIGHT RISE Contact List, posted on the project repository (Sharepoint) and accessible at all times to all ENLIGHT RISE project members.

Note: any change in representatives in one of the different governance levels can be entered directly in the file and must be doubled by an email to the ENLIGHT RISE project coordination for information.

3. Project workplan and implementation

The ENLIGHT RISE project consists of a 3-year programme of the ENLIGHT European University Alliance to establish a joint research and innovation agenda with and for society.

It consists of three blocks: Means and Methods, Foundations, and Opening & co-creating. Together these form the basis for nine (9) interrelated work packages.

Collaborative work across work packages ensures smooth communication between the three blocks.

3.1. Work packages description

WP1 Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda	
Lead	UT (Co-leads RUG & UBx)
Content	WP1 will set-up a joint Research and Innovation Support Group (R&I-SG). The R&I-SG will develop a plan for sustainable and synergistic coordination of R&I support activities and identify relevant funding supports, fostering R&I collaborations on ENLIGHT flagship challenges. WP1 will develop a harmonized approach for researcher/funding matching within the ENLIGHT alliance, with specific software development.
WP2 (Create synergies through R&I capacity building)	
Lead	UGent (Co-leads UPV and UBx)
Content	WP2 will analyse the ENLIGHT universities' scientific and technological profiles, individually and in connection with each other, identifying the areas where the alliance has the highest competitive advantage. Identified R&I synergies will provide the R&I-SG (see WP1) with broad orientations for prioritizing R&I support activities. WP2 will set up an ENLIGHT R&I Observatory centralizing these and other benchmarking and survey results from all WPs. WP2 will support three pilot

	actions, with the creation of pilot focus groups, supported by protected time for community building activities of researchers, and seed funding.
WP3 (Roadmap towards shared digital research infrastructures and responsible DI/AI index)	
Lead	UU (Coleads UGOE, UT and UBx)
Content	WP3 will map digital research infrastructures of relevance to the five ENLIGHT flagship challenges and develop a roadmap for sharing them across the alliance and facilitating their interoperability. WP3 will furthermore enhance connections with European digital infrastructures. Finally, WP3 will propose a responsible DI/AI development index to benchmark and maximize the positive impact of DI/AI on the ENLIGHT flagship challenges.
WP4 (Promote early career development & improve researcher assessment)	
Lead	CU (Co-leads UGent & NUI Galway)
Content	WP4 will seek to develop attractive career frameworks for researchers. WP4 will on the one hand launch strong complementary actions to support early career development within the alliance (through networking, mentoring and leadership training), and on the other hand propose innovative solutions to modernize researcher assessment systems, in order to better reward diverse and engaged career paths.
WP5 (Roadmap for an ENLIGHT European innovation district)	
Lead	NUI Galway (Co-leads UU & CU)
Content	WP5 will develop a map of academy-industry partnerships and set up an ENLIGHT European Innovation District with an ENLIGHT Innovation Network of academy-industry collaborators and the organization of Academy Industry Meeting days. The ENLIGHT European innovation district will benchmark sustainable development related academy-industry partnerships, centred on the 5 flagship challenges, and boost entrepreneurial and innovation capacity.
WP6 (Co-create R&I actions with society)	
Lead	RUG (Co-leads UPV/EHU & CU)
Content	WP6 will foster genuine engagement of civil society actors (citizens, civil society organizations, communities, municipalities, non-profits/3rd sector) in ENLIGHT R&I (from setting research agendas, to executing the research, analysing

	and interpreting findings and discussing follow-up and creating impact), thus co-creating knowledge, as well as including students in this collaboration.
WP7 (Optimize Open Science practices and identify frontiers)	
Lead	UGOE (Co-leads UGent & UT)
Content	WP7 will improve Open Science (OS) support practices among ENLIGHT partners by developing common approaches for assessing OS efforts of research staff, recognizing excellence in doing so, and for training support staff and researchers on how to engage with the public and make their results accessible. WP7 will develop and implement joint actions in order to raise awareness, and to transform the way researchers and other stakeholders create, store, share, and review research outputs
WP8 (Impact assessment and frontiers of the common R&I agenda)	
Lead	UPV/EHU (Co-lead NUI Galway)
Content	WP8 will expand methods developed for impact-driven teaching and training within the ENLIGHT alliance to mission and impact-driven research and innovation. In parallel, WP8 will explore the frontiers of a common R&I agenda and analyse the regulatory, administrative, social, and other barriers encountered within the ENLIGHT RISE project. Finally, WP8 will share intelligence on these aspects with all other funded European University Alliances as part of the FOREU(2) initiative.
WP9 Management, Dissemination and Exploitation	
Lead	UBx (Co-leads UGent & UGOE)
Content	WP9 will ensure efficient and effective management of the ENLIGHT RISE project in accordance with the ENLIGHT alliance overall management structure and objectives. It will contribute to ensuring that the project is carried out in accordance with the work plan and that project progress is regularly monitored and reported on to ensure proper corrective measures are timely implemented. It will ensure that efficient communication is maintained across the consortium on all legal, contractual, ethical, financial and administrative issues and with the EC. It will verify that communication, dissemination and exploitation of the results are implemented and updated.

3.2. Workplan

The workplan is available on the ENLIGHT RISE proposal Part B annexed to the Grant Agreement p24 ([GA PART B Workplan](#)) and updated in Sharepoint [link here](#)

4. Reporting and payments: the lump sum approach

The ENLIGHT RISE project is a H2020 lump sum project. It refers to the [Lump Sum Pilot Model Grant Agreement \(MGA\)](#). And the [Annotated Model Grant Agreement](#) (Lump Sum Pilot MGA from p.815) available in the SharePoint.

In that sense, there are obligations to fulfil and management that may differ from standard H2020 grants.

4.1. Lump sum project management

4.1.1. Principles

The lump sum for the grant is set out at its signature; one lump sum share is fixed in the grant agreement for each work package. For reporting, the costs actually incurred are not relevant.

The reporting periods and technical reporting focus on the completion of work packages rather than on financial reporting.

It means that no actual costs should be reported to the EC; there are no costs eligibility rules, and no financial audits will be carried out. Consequently, also for internal reporting no financial report will be asked from the project partners.

4.1.2. Checks, reviews and audits

The checks, reviews and audits thus focus on:

- Proper implementation of the action (e.g. technical audit)
- Compliance with the other obligations of the grant agreement (IPR obligations; obligations related to third parties; ethics, visibility of EU funding...)

As a consequence,

- 1), any document facilitating any kind of proof that a (specific) workload has been done (as agreed with the EC/REA) must be kept for audit (i.e. meeting minutes and lists of attendees, technical documents, publications, prototypes, deliverables and information detailing the exact role of each partner university in every WP and deliverable...);
- 2) there is no need for time sheets, pay slips or contracts, depreciation policy, travel invoices, actual costs.

Hence it is imperative that all ENLIGHT RISE activities and products are well documented, well stored and archived. In order to facilitate this, the ENLIGHT RISE repository (SharePoint environment) has been created to which all ENLIGHT RISE partners and task members have access to, and all are very strongly encouraged to upload all proof of any activity related to the ENLIGHT RISE project (Work packages). This, of course, in order to facilitate a sound and complete technical reporting.

4.2. Lump sum project reporting obligations

For **technical Periodic Report**, the obligations are the same as for standard H2020 grants:

- Explanation of the work carried out (narrative part). The template is the same as for H2020 grants but the section on "Use of resources" is not applicable
- Overview of the progress, towards the objectives of the action, including work packages, milestones and deliverables as agreed with EC
- Summary for publication
- Questionnaire

For **financial periodic report**, individual financial statements are signed by FSIGN of each partner. They must declare the lump sum share for the WP that has been completed in the reporting period. In practice, the individual statements will be pre-filled with lump sum shares for completed WP, based on the declaration of the coordinator in the "Status of Work Packages" table in the Grant Management Services in the Funding & Tenders Portal.

4.3. Interim payment

As abovementioned, a set share of the project lump sum has been allocated to each individual Work package (WP). The respective share of a WP will be paid by the EC/REA to the project coordinator via a set scheme of interim payments.

The interim payment for a respective WP, however, will only be effectuated once the respective WP has been fully completed, all its deliverables and milestones have been uploaded onto the EC portal, and the WP reporting has been approved by the EC/REA. WPs that have not been completed in time or cannot be approved at the time of an interim payment will not receive funding, though may be submitted for the next reporting period (or any other future reporting period, after they have been completed) upon which they can still be funded considering the previously mentioned conditions. Consequently, the coordination ENLIGHT partner will only transfer the respective amount of the lump sum to the WP beneficiary partners, once the WP workload has been fully finished, approved by the EC/REA and the respective WP lump sum has been transferred to the ENLIGHT RISE coordinating partner.

4.4. Amendments

The procedure is described in art 55 of the lump sum pilot MGA. This is the same procedure to submit amendment as for H2020 standard grants.

The coordinator submits request for amendment on behalf of the beneficiaries, through the electronic exchange system in the Funding Portal.

WP leaders or ENLIGHT RISE main contacts shall get in touch with the project coordinator and project manager as soon as they identify the need for an amendment related to the WP they are responsible for.

Any amendment is discussed in the ENLIGHT RISE Project Board Meeting with all WP leaders to assess the potential impact of the amendment on ongoing activities in other WP and partner institutions. The proposed amendment must be validated by the Project Board prior to launching the official process with the European Commission; the Directors' meeting should be informed.

4.5. Lump sum grant – Budget transfers

All lump sum share transfers require an amendment (see art 4.2 of lump sum pilot MGA).

The transfers may be:

- Within the same work package (i.e. increasing the share of a partner and decreasing the share of another)
- Between work packages (i.e. increasing the share allocated to a work package and decreasing the share of another)

The transfer amounts between WPs will be only acceptable if:

- WPs have not already been completed (and declared)
- In exceptional circumstances, it is justified in light of the technical and scientific implementation of the action
- A review confirms that it does not call into question the decision awarding the grant nor breaches the principle of equal treatment

However, there is no need for amendment for a transfer within the same work package benefiting the same partner.

5. Consortium communication

5.1. General practical communication issues

The ENLIGHT RISE community will use the same templates already implemented by the ENLIGHT E+ community (PowerPoint, Deliverables, others). However, the templates are adapted to the H2020 funding (EU logo) and [available in SharePoint](#).

In all communication (documents/reports, presentations...), the EU funding logo as well as the following sentence must be included

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035819"

Further information is provided in the deliverable *D9.4 "Project communication plan."*

We recall here the communication management strategy defined for the ENLIGHT E+ project as the same rules apply to the ENLIGHT RISE project.

5.2. Internal Communication tools: MS TEAMS and SHAREPOINT

As for the ENLIGHT E+ project, ENLIGHT RISE uses MS TEAMS and SHAREPOINT for internal communication and file sharing/storing (ENLIGHT RISE Repository). The coordinator owns a specific account and overlooks the technical maintenance and well use.

- **MS Teams:** Microsoft Teams is a cloud-based team collaboration software that is part of the Office 365 suite of applications. The core capabilities in Microsoft Teams include business messaging, calling, video meetings and file sharing.

[Link to ENLIGHT RISE MS TEAM](#)

- **SharePoint:** Microsoft SharePoint is a web-based platform used for sharing files and information. It is designed for teams and provides collaboration features, such as project management, messaging, and shared document storage.

[Link to ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint](#)

The ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint site is complemented with MS Teams channels.

NOTE: only the ENLIGHT RISE coordinator can invite additional persons to join the MS TEAMS and SHAREPOINT. Persons have been invited according to the contact list. In case of change of persons, please send an email to the project coordinator and project manager to add/change access rights to the relevant persons.

5.2.1. Instant communication/group chat/meetings

For ENLIGHT RISE we will use MS Teams as a tool for instant communication and discussion chats. The different channels are public to the ENLIGHT RISE members to

ensure transparency among the WPs. There are channels for the different governing boards and for the WPs.

MS Teams should be used as a communication tool, not for storing or sharing of documents, for which SharePoint is the tool to be used. Only the SharePoint link of a specific document shall be shared in MS Teams, not the document itself. WPs or task teams who decide to store drafts and working documents in MS Teams "documents", should ensure to store final documents on the ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint environment.

Content of MS TEAMS

- **Channels** are dedicated spaces that enable chat and instant discussion in pre-determined groups.

The following channels have been created for the ENLIGHT RISE project

- o One channel per WP, with notifications for all WP members as listed in the contact list (add the link)
 - o One general channel for general project questions (not related to a specific WP)
 - o One channel for the Project Board (private channel: accessible only to Project Board members)
- **Tags** in Ms Teams allow you to quickly reach one group of people at a time. One tag per WP group has been created and can be used to reach WP members: Write "@WP1/2/3 etc." to tag your colleagues and draw their attention to your message.

The other tags are:

@Mainliaison to reach all ENLIGHT RISE main liaison contacts

@WP leaders to reach all ENLIGHT RISE WP leaders

@WP leads and co leads to reach all ENLIGHT RISE WP leaders and co-leaders

Note: only the coordinator can add persons in the different tag groups and WP channels. Persons have been listed according to the contact list (*available on SharePoint*). Any change in this excel contact list shall be doubled by an email to the coordinator and project manager so that the change is also reflected in the WP channels and existing tags.

New tags can be created upon request, it can be discussed during the project board meeting.

- **Using MS Teams for meeting**

- It is encouraged to meet as much as possible in the ENLIGHT RISE MS teams channels, to allow transparency and conversation history. If you send out a regular MS Teams invitation, there is no trace back to the ENLIGHT RISE community.

- Currently no meetings can be scheduled via "agenda" in MS Teams, as when this would be done, the whole ENLIGHT RISE community would automatically receive the invitation, (around several hundreds of persons!).
- A solution is to schedule a normal meeting via Outlook and copy-paste the link of the relevant channel in the Outlook invitation.
- To link to the channel:
 - Click on the channel concerned in MS Teams: either right click on the name of the channel or click on the 3 dots: "get link to channel".
 - Click on the 3 dots in the right upper corner of the channel concerned.
 - The meeting can start in the channel by clicking "meet now", right upper corner in the channel. Starting simultaneous meetings should be avoided, it is recommended that the host starts the meeting some 10 min earlier.

3
Start the meeting

- Note: people should be a member of the MS Teams ENLIGHT RISE group before they can join the meeting.

5.2.2. File storing and sharing

We will use SharePoint as a tool for file storing and sharing.

The ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint focuses on project management mainly, enabling the monitoring of the project implementation.

Content of SharePoint

- Archive of Agendas and Reports (of all formal management bodies)
- Library for official documents (Project description, Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement)
- Workspaces (WP channels)

As a repository, all important documents and proofs of work (minutes of meetings, attendance list, draft of surveys...) must be stored in the ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint for monitoring purpose and potential audits.

The ENLIGHT RISE Coordination recommends all ENLIGHT RISE members to save all important documents on the dedicated (WPs) space or file as ENLIGHT RISE content is being produced.

It is the responsibility of WP leaders to store in the dedicated WP space all the documents proving the WP advancement:

- WP meetings: minutes, attendance list, slides -> all WP members are expected to fill out the dedicated Excel 'meeting & decisions archive' in the respective WP folder.
- Draft of deliverables
- Workshops towards external stakeholders: invitations, slides, minutes, attendance list and promotional actions
- Any other document proving WP work.

REMARK: It is important to clarify that both the ENLIGHT E+ and the ENLIGHT RISE project have their own separate SharePoint repository. For common issues however, (agenda and minutes Director's meetings, common strategy papers, etc.) the ENLIGHT E+ SharePoint will be used as the ENLIGHT Alliance repository. Henceforward all ENLIGHT RISE members have been granted access to the ENLIGHT E+ SharePoint and MS Teams (which vice versa is not the case.)

5.3. Internal information flows

Internal information flows can be on two levels: between the ENLIGHT RISE coordination and the individual partner institutions and within ENLIGHT RISE WPs and across the governance and management boards.

5.3.1. Between ENLIGHT RISE coordination/governance and individual partner institutions

Each institution makes the following provisions:

- Each institution provides an institutional ENLIGHT/ENLIGHT RISE email address to act as a “main liaison” for the ENLIGHT RISE project;
- Each institution appoints persons who play a central role in the communication process:
 - o For each institution the resp. vice-rector/vice-president/director for research or internationalization plays a central role in the communication and decision making between his/her institution and the ENLIGHT alliance regarding strategic issues. This person takes part in the Executive Committee.
 - o Academic or administrative coordinator/leader
 - o Each institution appoints one of its institutional coordinators who takes part in the Project Board, as “main liaison” to act as single point of contact for all communication between their institution and the ENLIGHT RISE coordination.
- In practical terms the main liaison manages the institutional ENLIGHT RISE email address. On the one hand they capture data from the own institution to pass them to consortium, on the other hand, they dispatche/disseminate all information from the consortium to the right depts. and/or persons within the own institution (using the designated institutional communication channels). Therefore, it is crucial that the main liaison contacts are in copy of all ENLIGHT RISE communication and have access to the SharePoint document libraries and MS Teams channels.
- When only one institutional ENLIGHT alliance email address covers both the ENLIGHT RISE as well as the ENLIGHT E+ project, it is the responsibility at each university level to ensure transparency and directional information between the ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE coordinating teams.

5.3.2. Within ENLIGHT RISE WPs and across the governance and management boards

The challenge is double:

- ensure proper follow-up at each university level so that feedbacks to surveys are provided as appropriate
- enable WP leaders to monitor quickly questions/results from other WPs that are relevant for their own tasks

Linked to the execution of the ENLIGHT RISE project, there are several flows of communication across the governance boards, work packages and task members. A major dimension concerns the organisation of the different WP Executive Teams.

Each WP executive team organises its own internal information flow between its members (frequency of meetings and communication).

However, in order to keep transparency and to keep information accessible, it is advised to include the respective institutional ENLIGHT RISE main liaison in copy of all circular communication (including emails to WP task experts). It is also recommended to use the dedicated MS Teams channels and SharePoint workspaces for file sharing, to enable the main liaisons to keep an overview of all information flows.

In the ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint, there is a dedicated section to store survey questions and results along the way (not waiting for the deliverables to be produced). This can benefit the whole community and will be easier to spot if all in the same file.

5.4. External information flows

Apart from the internal information flows, there are external information flows between the ENLIGHT RISE consortium and several external stakeholders.

The external communication strategy is detailed in the deliverables D9.4 "*Communication Action Plan*", and D9.5 "*Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results (PEDR)*" which are consultable on the [Sharepoint](#).

6. Quality process for deliverables and milestones publication

In order to guarantee the successful completion and the quality of the tasks and deliverables in the framework of the ENLIGHT RISE project, a quality assurance plan is foreseen to be developed for ENLIGHT RISE.

6.1. Quality process for deliverables

- Each deliverable once completed shall be sent prior one month to the delivery date to EC to the WP members for internal validation using the [template](#) available in the ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint
- At least one (1) month prior to delivery date, once validated internally, the WP

- leader shall send the deliverable + a summary of the content to the ENLIGHT RISE coordinator and project manager (UBx)
- The ENLIGHT RISE coordinator and project manager will send the deliverable to the project Board members for review.
 - The deliverable is presented and approved at the next Project Board meeting.
 - Once validated by the Project Board's meeting, the deliverable is
 - o 1) uploaded on the [SharePoint](#) for information/dissemination and applicability within the ENLIGHT community
 - o 2) uploaded by the ENLIGHT RISE Project Manager (UBx) in the ENLIGHT RISE portal of the European Commission
 - o 3) Sent for information to the Executive Secretary for the Directors' information.

 - The validation process shall take around one month

Public deliverables are made available on the Zenodo community of the project.

[Access here.](#)

After upload on the European Commission's portal, a version with a disclaimer "Draft awaiting European Commission approval" is published on Zenodo. When the deliverable is approved by the European Commission, a final version is uploaded with the CC-BY logo on the first page.

6.2. Quality process for milestones

The validation process for milestones is similar to the one for deliverables.

- Once achieved, a milestone (delivery date and a short text (max two sentences) explaining the milestones achievement) shall be sent to the WP members for internal validation;
- Once validated internally, the Work Package leader shall send the short text + delivery date to the ENLIGHT RISE coordinator and project manager (UBx).
- Displayed at the next Project Board's meeting, the milestone is
 - o 1) integrated in the Deliverables & Milestones dashboard of the project available on ENLIGHT RISE Sharepoint (Link)
 - o 2) uploaded by the ENLIGHT RISE Project Manager (UBx) in the ENLIGHT RISE portal of the European Commission.

Opportunities to extend the Q&A task force implemented in the ENLIGHT E+ project to the ENLIGHT RISE project will be discussed.

7. Risk monitoring

As described, several bodies and processes are in place to monitor the ENLIGHT RISE project implementation and to identify potential risks to happen.

7.1. Management bodies and processes

7.1.1. Co-coordination

WP9 is responsible for the day-to-day ENLIGHT RISE coordination and management. One of its tasks is the monitoring of ENLIGHT RISE progress against the main risks identified. This will enable proper risk assessment and any necessary corrective actions to be implemented in a timely fashion.

The Co-coordinators (UBx and UGent) meet on a weekly basis to discuss the overall implementation of the project and issues at hand. Those meetings are jointly organised for ENLIGHT E+ and ENLIGHT RISE on a strategic level (and bring together the academic coordinators, the ENLIGHT Executive Secretary and the project managers, as well as the Chair and Vice-Chair of the Directors' meeting).

7.1.2. Work package co-leading process

Furthermore, several bodies and meetings enable the monitoring of each task and the prevention of risks to happen.

Considering that, for each WP we have a leader and co-leader(s) that are responsible for the proper implementation of the tasks. Risks can be identified if any and solution can be proposed.

For every WP, regular meetings are planned:

- between the whole WP executive team (mostly on a monthly basis)
- between the WP co-leads (once a month or every 15 days)

7.1.3. Project Board meetings and Executive Committee

See table section 2.2

7.2. List of potential risks and mitigation measures identified

Description of risk (level of likelihood: Low/Medium/High)	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
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Difficulty identifying R&I-SG Personnel (low)	1	Staff already identified at proposal stage
COVID affects ability to bring researchers together (medium)	1	Use of digital tools for matching
Technical barriers to digital matching tool (low)	1	Based upon already implemented technology being used in UT
Resistance to uptake of the matching tool by researchers (low)	1	In the pilot phase prioritized researchers identified in WP2 as deriving a high added value from ENLIGHT partnerships
Difficulty in collection information on patents etc. from all universities (low)	2	Prioritize publicly available information
Lacking internal resources to build and update the R&I Observatory (low)	2	Outsourcing will be considered for web interface
IP protection and legal aspects of data sharing (medium)	3	Together with the human resource, financial and legal departments of the different universities, common procedures are being developed in ENLIGHT E+ to remove legal barriers for access to research infrastructure etc.
Difficulty to identify members for the DI/AI network in partner universities and associated partners (medium)	3	Not all partners need to be involved in this pilot phase. A core group of at least 4 universities will be targeted (WP (co-)leads)
Low engagement of doctoral/early-career researchers (medium)	4	Proper planning to target the time-constraints, offer virtual participation, enhance communication
Unwillingness to share HR related information (medium)	4	We have the commitment of highest

		management to the deliverables
Difficulty in collecting comprehensive academic-industry collaboration data (low)	5	Collect data that industries are open to share
Limited success with stakeholder engagement in particular from non-partner groups (medium)	5	Strong connections with stakeholders underpin the ENLIGHT ensuring their commitment; development of a comprehensive engagement strategy;
Low uptake of engagement with researchers in proposed OS activities, e.g. recruitment of ambassadors (medium)	7	Target the ones which are already committed first (in particular early career researchers), and take into account barriers (e.g. time-constraints).
Low number of submissions for Open Science Award (medium)	7	Use high-level communication channels (e.g. president's and faculty newsletters, research committee meetings, career office)
R&I Impact culture and literacy is detected to be low among ENLIGHT individuals and entities (low)	8	Rapid engagement of Impact champions that can be shown as examples to follow and lead a movement towards a culture of impact
Difficulty to reach consensus on how to adopt a common framework for impact assessment and to implement impact-driven R&I agendas (medium)	8	Gradual, stepping-stone approach to define impact assessment in a comfortable path adapted to the reality/rhythm of partner universities

Reluctance to engage in dialogue and agreements between European Universities Alliances to set up common interest areas and to speak with a single voice (medium)	8	Establish continuous conversations at different institutional levels (governance, operational structures), and maintain an open attitude to share information, and success as well as failure stories
Continuation of Covid 19 pandemic (medium)	9, all	Conferences and meetings will be organised online
Limited partner engagement and/or underperformance (low)	9	Regular Internal reporting to allow project coordination team to identify potential issues and address them by remediation actions
Dissemination/Communication tools put in place are not the most effective for the target groups (low)	9	The communication tools have been used by partners for previous projects in their countries and have proved to be effective. An evaluation of the effectiveness of the tools will be carried out annually and reviewed accordingly
Turnover of key-personnel, including top management of partner universities (low)	9	Standardizing the procedures, to be shared with new key personnel
Schedule slippage, late deliveries and slow progress in general (low)	9	Periodic progress status assessments conducted by WP leaders and reported to the coordinator and the ENLIGHT Project Board as part of progress reports

8. Conclusion

This management handbook is an active document. This handbook is intended to evolve and be enriched as the project is implemented. Updates could be made.